

REVIVING TRADITIONAL JAMU: THE CREATION OF HERBALIS MILK IN KELURAHAN KARYA JAYA, TEBING TINGGI

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Abstract

Kelurahan Karya Jaya is a community where a significant number of people engage in jamu production. The community service program Revitalizing Traditional Jamu: The Development of Herbalis Milk in Kelurahan Karya Jaya, Tebing Tinggi aims to strengthen the potential of traditional jamu by innovating their presentation into herbal-based milk products. Jamu, one of Indonesia's cultural heritage, is frequently viewed as unappealing to younger generations because of its bitter flavor and traditional presentation. Transforming jamu into herbal milk not only enhances its taste but also boosts its nutritional benefits and makes it more acceptable to consumers, particularly children and young people. The problems identified include limited knowledge of residents in product diversification, lack of skills in hygienic and modern processing, and minimal access to packaging technology that is attractive and marketable. To resolve these challenges, we provide training and workshops on turning jamu into herbalis milk, practical guidance and direct teaching during the production process, as well as assistance in packaging and marketing strategies. This activity is expected to revitalize the traditional jamu culture, create added economic value for the community, and open wider market opportunities through innovative herbal milk products. The methods used in this service activity are training and practice, mentoring, and monitoring and evaluation.

Keyword: *Jamu, herbalis milk,*

1. Introduction

Jamu, Indonesia's traditional herbal beverage, has long been acknowledged as a cultural heritage that embodies centuries of wisdom in health and wellness (Elfahmi et al., 2014). Made from natural ingredients like roots, leaves, spices, and medicinal plants, jamu has been used for generations as both a preventive measure and a healing remedy (Putra & Abryanto, 2021). Beyond its health functions, jamu also show an important aspect of Indonesian identity, portray the close relationship between culture, health, and nature. In recent decades, shifts in lifestyle, and contemporary consumer preferences have led to a gradual decrease in jamu consumption, especially among younger (Amalia et al., 2017). Because the factor such as its bitter taste, strong aroma, and less convenient preparation methods have contributed to its declining popularity. Jamu represents a beautiful blend of tradition and modernity. Each serving of jamu reveals a smooth link between history and the future, offering us health benefits while also preserving Indonesia's rich cultural identity and heritage. We can celebrate jamu as the essence of Indonesian culture, nurturing us today and for future generations (Nurcholis & Arianti, 2024). However, public awareness of health and nutrition has grown, arising in a higher demand for beverages that are nutritious and beneficial for immunity and overall well-being. This trend opens up possibilities to revitalize jamu through innovations that maintain its health benefits while making it more attractive to contemporary consumers (Khalid, 2024). One exciting development is herbalis milk, which merges the nutritional advantages of milk with the healing properties of jamu. By converting jamu into a milk-based drink, it becomes more enjoyable, less bitter, and more acceptable to a broader audience, especially children, teenagers, and young adults.

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Kelurahan Karya Jaya, Tebing Tinggi City, North Sumatra, is a neighborhood with cultural ties to traditional herbal practices. The local jamu products are mainly produced by the women's community group (PKK) and local jamu makers who have passed down this knowledge within generations. Despite this potential, challenges remain, including limited knowledge of product variation, lack of skills in hygienic and standardized processing, and minimal access to suitable equipment and modern packaging technologies. These obstacles hinder the ability of local producers to compete with modern health beverages and to capture wider market opportunities. To address these issues, the community service program Revitalizing Traditional Jamu: The Development of Herbalis Milk was carried out at the office of the village head (kantor lurah) of Kelurahan Karya Jaya. This activity included a series of training, workshops, and direct mentoring aimed at improving the knowledge and skills of PKK women and local jamu producers in making herbalis milk. Additionally, it provided support in packaging, branding, and marketing strategies to boost product competitiveness. By empowering the community through innovation, this initiative aims to preserve the heritage of jamu while also generating economic value, strengthening the local economy, and broadening access to larger markets. We experimented with several variations to create an optimal herbalis milk, targeting on the right balance between cow milk and jamu. After testing four different ratios (Tabel 1) and surveying 15 participants, we found that the most popular combination is 100 mL of cow milk mixed with 100 mL of jamu, addition by 0.5 grams of cinnamon, 0.5 grams of black pepper, and one teaspoon of honey. This mixture not only achieves a pleasant flavor but also enhances the health benefits of the drink, making it both enjoyable and nutritious.

Tabel 1. Variation between milk and jamu

Sample	Cow milk (mL)	Jamu (mL)
A	100	50
B	100	75
C	100	100
D	100	150

The shelf life of herbalis milk is strongly affected by storage conditions. When kept in a chiller at a temperature of 4–10 °C, the product can last between 6–8 days. Low temperatures help to slow down microbial growth, preserve freshness, and maintain the stability of both texture and flavor (Mafe et al., 2024). In contrast, when stored at room temperature (27–30 °C), herbalis milk is not stable, with an estimated shelf life of only 12–24 hours. Longer exposure to warmer conditions accelerates microbial activity, leading to changes in taste, odor, and color that reduce product quality, taste and safety (Barcenilla et al., 2022). Therefore, refrigeration is highly recommended as the primary method to store the herbalis milk to extend product shelf life and ensure consumer safety and health.

Tabel 2. Shelf life in different storage condition

Storage Condition	Temperature Range	Estimated Shelf Life	Notes
Chiller (Refrigerated)	4 – 10 °C	6 – 8 days	Maintains freshness, slows bacterial growth, texture and taste remain stable
Room Temperature	27 – 30 °C	12 – 24 hours	Risk of microbial contamination increases, possible changes in taste, odor, and color

2. Methods

The implementation of this community service activity was divided into four main stages, namely introduction, socialization, training, and mentoring. These stages were designed to empower the women's community group (PKK) and local jamu producers in Kelurahan Karya Jaya, Tebing Tinggi City, North Sumatra, especially in developing herbalis milk. The activity took place at the office of the village head (kantor lurah) and was carried out in the following steps:

2.1 Introduction, Lectures and Discussions

At the initial stage, the community service team conducted lectures and discussions to deliver socialization materials about the innovation of processing traditional jamu into herbalis milk. This was done to provide basic knowledge and make bigger insights to the participants knowing product diversification, hygiene, and nutritional benefits. The session was interactive, involving questions, answers, and discussions so that the level of understanding could be measured and participants were encouraged to share their own experiences and challenges in jamu production.

2.2 Socialization of Benefits and How to

The participants were given explanations and example regarding the potential benefits of processing jamu into herbalis milk. These benefits include the creation of added value, product diversification, improved consumer acceptance, increased income potential and increase the targeted market . This stage aimed to build perception and motivation for participants to adopt innovation as part of their household economy and community-based entrepreneurship.

2.3 Explanation of Materials and Tools

The team explained the various materials and equipment used in the processing of herbalis milk. Emphasis was given to the functions of each tool and how to optimize their use in order to ensure safe and hygienic production. This step was important to enable participants to operate the equipment independently and sustainably in future production activities.

2.4 Training and Workshop on Herbalis Milk Processing

After receiving theoretical knowledge, participants took part in hands-on training sessions. Workshops were conducted to demonstrate the step-by-step process of producing herbalis milk with different formulations (milk combined with varying volumes of jamu). Through practice, participants were able to directly improve their skills, gain confidence, and verify the materials delivered in the lecture sessions.

3. Result and Discussion.

The community service activities in Kelurahan Karya Jaya, Tebing Tinggi, North Sumatra, were carried out through several meetings that combined theory, practice, and mentoring. The program centered on the development of herbalis milk—an innovation that blends the nutritional benefits of milk with the healing tradition of jamu.

3.1 First Meeting (May 25, 2025: Introduction, Lectures, and Discussion)

The first gathering, held at the office of the village head, opened with an introduction to the program and its goals. The session with PKK women and local jamu makers to talk about the potential of turning traditional jamu into another product (herbalis milk) to engage new customer. Through lectures and open discussion, participants learned how the combination of milk and herbal extracts could not only make jamu more appealing but also expand its market value. The conversation make them share their personal experiences in producing and selling jamu, as well as challenges like limited packaging options and product storage issues. This made the place feel like a place where everyone was learning and excited about new ideas.

Figure 1. The first gathering with PKK women and local jamu makers

3.2 Training, Workshop, and Mentoring (August 4, 2025: Hands-on Development)

The second stage focused on hands-on learning. Participants worked directly with the community service team to practice turning jamu into herbalis milk. They learned everything step by step from how to prepare raw materials to how to mix milk with jamu in different ratio, to understanding proper hygiene throughout the process. Each participant had the chance to try for themselves, which built both confidence and skill. Mentoring was also provided,

ensuring that participants not only understood the techniques but felt ready to continue production independently.

Figure 2. Workshop

3.3 Laboratory Research and Testing

Alongside the workshops, laboratory research was executed to decide the most adequate ratio of milk to jamu. After testing several variations, the combination of 100 ml milk with 100 ml jamu proved to be the best balance. This ratio produced a drink that had a smooth taste and an appealing aroma, making it more acceptable to a wide range of consumers. The findings gave participants clear, practical guidance on which recipe to adopt for production.

Figure 3. Laboratory Research

3.4 Storage Trials

The program also included trials on storage conditions to conclude how long herbalis milk could stay fresh. When stored at room temperature (27–30 °C), the drink remained stable for only 12–24 hours before changes in taste and aroma became distinct. Under refrigerated conditions (4–10 °C), however, the storage life extended to 6–8 days, while keeping quality, taste and safety. This highlighted the importance of refrigeration for both household use and wider sales.

3.5 Discussion

These results show that uniting traditional knowledge with scientific research can create products that are both culturally significant and commercially feasible. The PKK women and local jamu producers not only get new

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knowledge but also hands-on skills that they can implement in their daily activities. With the 1:1 ratio as the recommended formula and refrigeration as the storage method, they are now ready to manufacture a healthier, tastier, and more market-ready beverage. To sum up, this initiative not only helps maintain the cultural value of jamu but also suggest new economic opportunities for the people of Kelurahan Karya Jaya. By embracing innovation while honoring tradition, the community has taken a step forward in revitalizing jamu for future generations.

Figure 4. socialization of herbal medicine in Karya Jaya Subdistrict

4. Conclusion.

The community service activity in Kelurahan Karya Jaya, Tebing Tinggi, North Sumatra, achieving presented the innovative creation of herbalis milk as a means to revitalize traditional jamu. Through a combination of socialization, training, workshop, and mentoring, the participants obtained valuable knowledge and applied skills in producing herbalis milk from cow milk and jamu. The laboratory trials validated that the optimal ratio for herbalis milk is 100 ml of milk combined with 100 ml of jamu, delivering a harmonious taste that is both nourishing and attractive to a wider audience.

The storage test also showed the importance of refrigeration, lengthening the product's shelf life to 6-8 days while maintaining its quality. This finding secures the long-term sustainability of herbalis milk production and its potential for market distribution.

Overall, the program not only enabled the local community by improving their skills and knowledge but also contributed to the economic development of Kelurahan Karya Jaya by creating a viable, value-added product. Through this action, the community can preserve their traditional herbal practices while tapping into modern market demands, ensuring the continued relevance and success of jamu in the contemporary health and wellness industry.

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